

Paquitop.arm: a camera-based mobile manipulator for indoor assistance

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Abstract— The use of automation and robotics technologies for care-giving and assistance has become a very interesting research topic in the last years. In this scenario, the researchers at Politecnico di Torino are working on Paquitop.arm, a mobile robot for assistive tasks, composed of an omnidirectional mobile platform, a 6 DOF robot arm, and a depth camera. Task-oriented considerations are made to estimate a set of mounting parameters which represents a trade-off between the exploitation of the robot arm workspace and the compactness of the entire system. A typical task is described to clarify the use of the robot in real applications.

Keywords— service robot, mobile manipulator, omnidirectional robot

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, many researchers in the robotic field investigated assistive robotics and developed several mobile robotic platforms conceived to help weak or non-self-sufficient subjects [1], [2]. The recent Covid-19 pandemic revealed the importance of social distancing, especially in those structures, such as geriatric wards and hospices, where patients are endangered by the closeness to other people [3]. Although human care cannot be replaced entirely (e.g., for complex operations and companionship), properly conceived and instrumented robots can be entrusted with other minor relevance duties. Blood pressure, temperature, and oxygen saturation measurements, patients monitoring, or simply providing a connectivity platform for remote communication, are some examples of tasks that could be easily assessed without the presence of humans.

These are the premises that led the researchers at Politecnico di Torino to develop an innovative mobile platform, named Paquitop [4], [5], as the base modular frame for indoor robotized assistance applications. The base platform, shown in Fig. 1(a) is suspended on four wheels: two of them are driven steering wheels, while two are standard off-centered passive castor wheels. Due to its particular aim, the robot was shaped on a human scale, to access all the spaces which are usually lived by persons. Therefore, a non-axisymmetric footprint has been adopted so that the robot can offer a reduced size to pass through confined spaces. At last, a preliminary analysis for the implementation of a robotic arm on the Paquitop platform, named Paquitop.arm, was proposed by authors in [6].

The updated prototype Paquitop.arm includes a robotic arm manipulator to allow the platform to enhance the machine capability of interaction with its surroundings and perform assistive tasks. The chosen manipulator is the 6 DOF Kinova

Fig. 1. (a) Render of the Paquitop mobile platform; (b) functional scheme of the Paquitop.arm system and reference frames definition.

Gen3 Lite, with a reach of 1 m, a nominal payload of 0.5 kg, and an overall mass of 5.2 kg. As it is reported in Fig. 1(a), the collaborative robot is installed on a mounting structure that enables different mounting configurations.

In Fig. 1(b) the main reference frames of Paquitop.arm are defined. The position and orientation of the mobile platform with respect to a fixed reference frame $\{s\}$ is defined through the frame $\{c\}$, fixed to the platform and positioned in the centre of the elliptical footprint at ground level. Moreover, the reference frame $\{0\}$ represents the base frame of the robotic arm, while $\{e\}$ the end-effector frame.

II. TASK DESCRIPTION

To fully perceive and obtain information from the surroundings, exteroceptive systems must be adopted. To provide such information a camera lidar Intel RealSense L515 is mounted fixed to the fifth link of the arm, as shown in Fig. 1(b). The camera uses an infra-red (IR) laser beam to scan its entire field of view (FOV), which is reflected and re-captured by an IR photodiode. Such data are processed to generate depth cloud points as output, which represents the entire FOV

Fig. 2. Overall architecture for autonomous task execution.

area. With the use of image recognition techniques, the camera will both recognize the object (such as door handles, lift buttons, bottles, glasses, etc) and calculate an associated reference frame. Once the posture of the robot is known, this information can be converted into the position and orientation of the object with respect to the base frame of the robot, allowing it to reach the object and interact with it. To better clarify how the system will work in real applications, Fig. 2 presents the overall architecture for autonomous task execution.

III. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents a mobile manipulator for indoor assistance applications. The system is composed of an omnidirectional mobile robot (named Paquitop) and a commercial light-weighted collaborative arm (Kinova Gen3 LITE) with 6 axes. In recent works, the mounting and the system performance have been evaluated in static conditions, together with its exteroceptive sensors system. It is worth remarking that one of the most interesting features of the proposed system is represented by its reduced weight, which makes it particularly feasible for home applications. As a side effect, special attention must be put to the stability of the whole system which can become critical under particular motion conditions. Thus, future investigations must be performed to ensure the

dynamic stability of the whole system with specific planning algorithms.

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